

PROMPT ENGINEERING FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY EXERCISES

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Abstract: This article presents methodological recommendations for the effective use of prompt engineering in designing materials for the development of lexical competence. It justifies the necessity of combining the classic PPP (Presentation, Practice, Production) model with the capabilities of AI for the comprehensive study of lexical units. It is emphasized that vocabulary instruction requires a systematic approach, including the development of skills related to form (spelling, pronunciation), meaning, usage in context, and collocations.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), prompt engineering, foreign language teaching methodology, vocabulary instruction, PPP model (Presentation-Practice-Production), lexical competence, collocations, contextual learning, pedagogical technologies, professional teacher training

ПРОМПТ-ИНЖИНИРИНГ ДЛЯ СОЗДАНИЯ ИНОЯЗЫЧНЫХ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ

Аннотация: Данная статья представляет собой методические рекомендации по эффективному использованию промпт-инжиниринга для проектирования материалов для формирования лексической компетенции. Обосновывается необходимость сочетания классической модели PPP (Presentation, Practice, Production) с возможностями ИИ для комплексной проработки лексических единиц. Подчеркивается, что обучение лексике требует системного подхода, включающего развитие навыков работы с формой (написание, произношение), значением, употреблением в контексте и коллокациями.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект (ИИ), промпт-инжиниринг, методика преподавания иностранных языков, обучение лексике, модель PPP (Presentation-Practice-Production), лексическая компетенция, коллокации, контекстуальное обучение, педагогические технологии, профессиональная подготовка учителей.

CHET TILI LEKSIK MASHQLARINI YARATISH UCHUN PROMPT-INJINIRING

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola leksik kompetensiyani shakllantirish uchun o'quv materiallarini loyihalashda prompt-injinirovdan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha uslubiy tavsiyalarni taqdim etadi. Leksik birliklarni kompleks o'zlashtirish uchun klassik PPP (Presentation, Practice, Production) modelini sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlari bilan uyg'unlashtirish zarurati asoslab beriladi. Leksikani o'qitish tizimli yondashuvni talab qilishi, jumladan, shakl (yozilish, talaffuz), ma'no, kontekstda qo'llash va kollokatsiyalar ustida ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish muhimligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt (SI), prompt-injinirovdan, xorijiy tillarni o'qitish metodikasi, leksikani o'qitish, PPP modeli (Presentation-Practice-Production), leksik kompetensiya, kollokatsiyalar, kontekstual ta'lim, pedagogik texnologiyalar, o'qituvchilarni kasbiy tayyorlash.

Introduction Nowadays, AI, in the system of education, is becoming an important tool for the teacher. The rapid advancement of generative artificial intelligence (AI), particularly large

language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, has opened new educational frontiers, providing scalable and personalised support for learners across diverse domains.(3) However, the quality of the generated content depends directly on the skill of crafting queries or, so called, prompt engineering. Students are chatting with the LLM but without any real purpose.(2) For future foreign language teachers, it is crucial to understand that teaching vocabulary requires a systematic approach, encompassing not only mechanical memorization but also deep work with form, meaning, usage in context, and collocations. With the right prompts, AI can be a powerful tool for developing vocabulary materials that incorporate repetition without making the learning process feel mechanical or monotonous. The purpose of this article is to structure the application of prompt engineering within the PPP model. The use of generative models requires clear algorithmization at each stage of learning. At the Presentation stage, the focus is on creating contextual scaffolds for semanticization. During Practice stage, exercises are generated to drill form, meaning, and combinability. Finally, Production stage involves designing situations for transferring the skill into speech.

Methods To ensure a systematic approach, prompt engineering must cover several critical aspects.. Just as clear and structured classroom instructions are crucial, prompts for AI should also be clear, specific, and contextually relevant. (1) When working with form, prompts must require the AI to create spelling exercises and phonetic tasks, including articulation descriptions and transcription. Below are examples of prompts you can use to effectively drill word form (spelling and pronunciation) with the help of AI. Prompts for working with spelling (orthography) can include the following tasks: "Create a gap-fill exercise to practice the spelling of the following 10 words: [add word list]. Include a task where students must correct intentional spelling errors of these same words in sentences." "Prepare an 'Anagram Scramble' task for the following vocabulary list: [word list]. Add a short definition-hint for each word." "Compile a list of 10 frequently misspelled words on the topic [topic]. Create a multiple-choice spelling exercise where the distractors (incorrect options) mimic students' typical errors." Prompts for working with pronunciation (phonetics and articulation) can use tasks such as: "For the following words: [word list], provide the IPA transcription. Also, give a step-by-step description of the articulation for each word: how to position the tongue, lips, and how the airflow is produced. Present this in a table for students." "Create a minimal pairs exercise to practice the sounds [e.g., /i:/ and /ɪ/]. Select 5 pairs of words that differ only by these sounds and write a short phonetic dictation with them." "Compile a list of difficult-to-pronounce words from the topic [topic]. For each word, offer a syllabification exercise and indicate the stressed syllable. Write two sentences with each word to practice rhythm and intonation."

Regarding meaning and context, it is necessary to request texts where the target vocabulary is presented in a natural environment. In matters of usage and collocations, the focus should be on creating "collocation matching" type tasks. To ensure that prompts yield methodologically accurate results, it is important to set clear context and combinability parameters for the AI. Examples of prompts for working with meaning and context include: "Write a short, natural dialogue (around 150 words) on the topic [topic] that organically uses the following lexical units: [word list]. Avoid artificial sentences where words are simply listed. The text should sound like everyday native speaker speech." "Create a case study for level [level] where the context makes the meaning of the word [word] obvious without without using a dictionary. Add 3 comprehension questions based on the text's context." "Write a short blog post or news article on the topic [topic]. Include [word list] in it. After the text, create a matching exercise where students must connect these words with contextual synonyms found in the text." Examples of prompts for working with usage and collocations include: "Create a list of 10 key collocations (verb+noun or adjective+noun) for the word [word]. Based on them, create a 'Collocation

Matching' exercise (column A with the beginning of the phrase, column B with the ending) so that students can assemble set phrases." "Develop an 'Odd One Out' exercise to test knowledge of collocations. For example, give 4 verbs, three of which collocate with [noun], and one that does not. Ask students to explain why one combination is impossible." "Prepare a gap-fill exercise where target words are omitted and surrounding text contains typical lexical clues (partner words) to help students choose the correct collocation. Provide an answer key with a short comment on why this specific combination is the most frequent." "Create a task requiring sentence paraphrasing: rewrite the given sentences to include the studied collocations with [word]. Compare the resulting sentences with the originals to show how collocations make speech more natural."

Results Integration into the PPP model through prompts looks as follows: at the presentation stage, a prompt might look like: "Create a short story at the B1 level using the following 5 words to highlight their meaning through context." For practice, it is advisable to use the request: "Develop an exercise to match these words with their definitions and collocations, as well as a sentence gap-fill task." At the production stage, the prompt might be: "Act as a discussion partner. We are discussing the given topic. Include questions in your responses that require the use of the studied collocations."

Discussion Prompt engineering transforms the teacher's role: from a consumer of ready-made materials, they become their architect. The systematic approach provided by prompts guarantees that students will not miss any aspect of lexical competence. However, students are often just chatting with the LLM without any real purpose. Future educators, MЭM, should remember that the generated result must always undergo critical verification for alignment with methodological goals and the students' age-specific needs.

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